

Studies on the Citrate Complex of Dimethyl Tin

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The complex formation of dimethyl tin with the citrate ligand has been studied by the pH titration method. The formation of a 1 : 1 type of complex is reported. A neutral complex (C) is formed below pH 3.4 which behaves like a tribasic acid and dissociates to complexes C_1^- , C_2^- and C_3^- and protons at higher pH. The equilibrium constants of the reactions,

$(CH_3)_2Sn^{++} + H_3Cit \rightleftharpoons C + 2H^+$, $C \rightleftharpoons C_1^- + H^+$, $C_1^- \rightleftharpoons C_2^- + H^+$ and $C_2^- \rightleftharpoons C_3^- + H^+$ are found to be 2.29×10^{-2} , 6.31×10^{-6} , 5.48×10^{-6} and 5.28×10^{-9} respectively.

YASUDA and Tobias^{1,2} have studied the complex formation of picolinic acid and phenanthroline with dimethyl tin. Since the citrate complex of this cation has not yet been studied, we thought it worthwhile to investigate this system.

Experimental

Four pH titrations were performed to investigate the complex formation. pH titrations were carried out by a Marconi pH meter (TF 1093/1) at 28°. The ionic strength is kept constant at 0.1M by the addition of potassium chloride. The dimethyl tin dichloride solution is prepared by dissolving a known amount of dimethyl tin dichloride in a known amount of hydrochloric acid solution to suppress the hydrolysis. This amount of acid is neutralised by KOH after the addition of citrate ligand. The experiments were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere.

Results and Discussion

The liberation of protons during the complex formation remains same when the metal to ligand ratio is increased from 1 : 1.25 to 1 : 5. The nature of the curves are also similar in both 1 : 1.25 and 1 : 5 ratio systems. This indicates the formation of a 1 : 1 type of complex. The horizontal distance increases in the beginning and then remains nearly constant upto pH 6.0 and then increases.

The reaction taking place in the experiment (I) can be represented as

$$K_1 = \frac{[C][H^+]^n}{[(CH_3)_2Sn^{++}][H_3Cit]} \quad \dots (1-i)$$

where C is the dimethyl tin citrate complex. The equilibrium constant is given by the equation (1-i).

It can be shown as in the case of cadmium citrate complex³, yttrium citrate⁴ and yttrium tartrate⁵ complex that

$$\frac{\Delta[NaOH] - \frac{a}{b}\Delta[Ct]}{[C]} = n - \frac{a}{b} \quad (2)$$

when the formation of the complex is complete

$$[C] = [(CH_3)_2SnCl_2]$$

Hence,

$$\frac{\Delta[NaOH] - \frac{a}{b}\Delta[Ct]}{[(CH_3)_2SnCl_2]} = n - \frac{a}{b} \quad \dots (2-i)$$

Fig. 1. pH titration of 100 ml of solution containing 0.000625 g moles of citric acid and 0.01 g moles of KCl (Curve A) and that of the same volume of another solution containing same quantity of the above constituents and 0.0005 g moles of dimethyl tin dichloride (Curve B) against 0.1N sodium hydroxide.

Fig. 2. pH titration of 100 ml of a solution containing 0.0025 g moles of citric acid and 0.01 g moles of KCl (Curve A) and that of the same volume of another solution containing the same quantity of the above constituents and 0.0005 g moles of dimethyl tin dichloride (Curve B) against 0.1N sodium hydroxide.

The values of n are calculated from the experiment (I) by equation (2-i) as in the case of cadmium citrate complex and are recorded in the Table 1. The value of n is found to be greater than 2, 3 and 4 above pH 3.6, 4.8 and 6.5 respectively. Below pH 3.6, a neutral complex is formed with the liberation of 2 protons. The formation of the complex C is complete at pH 3.6. The values of C are calculated below this pH by the equation (2) assuming the n values to be 2. The values of K were calculated and tabulated in the Table 1. The mean value of K is found to be 2.29×10^{-3} .

At and above pH 3.6, n is greater than 2 indicating the dissociation of the neutral complex C to C_1^- and H^+ according to the equation (3).

$$K_1 = \frac{[C_1^-][H^+]}{[C]} \quad (3-i)$$

It can be shown as before that,

$$K_1 = \frac{(n-2)[H^+]}{(3-n)}$$

The values of K calculated by the above equation are recorded in the Table 1. The mean value of K is 6.31×10^{-5} .

In higher pH (above 4.8) the complex C_1^- dissociates to C_2^{2-} and H^+ according to the equation (4). The equilibrium constant is represented by the equation (4-i).

$$K_2 = \frac{[C_2^{2-}][H^+]}{[C_1^-]} \quad (4-i)$$

Similarly it can be shown that

$$K_2 = \frac{(n-3)[H^+]}{(4-n)}$$

The values of K_2 are recorded in the Table 1 and the mean value is found to be 5.48×10^{-6} .

TABLE 1

pH	$\Delta[NaOH] \times 10^3$	$-\Delta[Cl] \times 10^4$	$[M] \times 10^3$	a/b	n	$[C] \times 10^3$	$[M^{++}] \times 10^4$	$[H_2Oit] \times 10^4$	$K \times 10^3$	$K_1 \times 10^4$	$K_2 \times 10^6$	$K_3 \times 10^9$
2.8	4.094	2.77	4.63	0.3588	1.2643	2.555	20.75	20.57	1.503			
3.0	4.397	3.0	4.565	0.4922	1.4769	2.993	15.72	14.18	1.343			
3.2	4.894	3.35	4.505	0.6197	1.7517	3.697	8.08	7.766	2.345			
3.4	4.804	3.28	4.465	0.7632	1.8952	4.089	3.76	4.31	3.99			
3.6	5.112	3.43	4.417	0.9078	2.1348	—	—	—	—	3.913		
3.8	4.808	3.26	4.378	1.052	2.229	—	—	—	—	4.707		
4.0	4.914	3.59	4.34	1.204	2.435	—	—	—	—	7.7		
4.2	4.807	3.28	4.291	1.362	2.586	—	—	—	—	8.932		
4.8	4.91	3.31	4.178	1.876	3.199	—	—	—	—	—	3.939	
5.0	4.67	3.16	4.151	2.049	3.330	—	—	—	—	—	4.925	
5.2	4.59	3.1	4.116	2.213	3.495	—	—	—	—	—	6.184	
5.4	4.5	3.05	4.083	2.374	3.493	—	—	—	—	—	3.371	
5.5	4.13	2.79	4.065	2.450	3.634	—	—	—	—	—	5.478	
5.8	4.07	2.75	4.033	2.654	3.843	—	—	—	—	—	8.509	
7.2	5.01	3.4	3.891	2.981	4.529	—	—	—	—	—	—	7.087
7.4	5.16	3.48	3.886	2.988	4.583	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.567
7.5	5.44	3.67	3.87	2.988	4.677	—	—	—	—	—	—	6.628
7.8	5.44	3.78	3.861	2.995	4.697	—	—	—	—	—	—	3.646
8.0	5.84	3.95	3.847	2.997	4.823	—	—	—	—	—	—	4.649
8.2	5.98	4.02	3.841	2.997	4.868	—	—	—	—	—	—	4.149

Above pH 6.5 the n values are greater than 4 indicating the formation of the complex C_3^{3-} .

$$K_s = \frac{[C_3^{3-}][H^+]}{[C_3^{2-}]} \quad \dots (5-i)$$

The equilibrium constant is calculated by the equation

$$K_s = \frac{(n-4)[H^+]}{(5-n)} \quad \dots (5-ii)$$

The mean value of K_s is 5.28×10^{-8} and recorded in the Table I.

The nature of curves in the Figures 3 and 4 are very similar. In the Fig. 4, the ratio of the metal to ligand is 1 : 5 and hence the formation of the complex is complete. The pH attained by the solution containing dimethyl tin by the addition of 11 ml of 0.1N NaOH is reached in the blank solution

Fig. 3. pH titration of 100 ml of a solution containing 0.0025 g moles of sodium citrate and 0.01 g moles of KCl (Curve A) and that of another solution of same volume containing the same quantity of the above constituents and 0.0005 g moles of dimethyl tin dichloride (Curve B) against 0.1N sodium hydroxide.

Fig. 4. pH titration of 100 ml of a solution containing 0.000625 g moles of sodium citrate and 0.01 g moles of KCl (Curve A) and that of another solution containing same quantity of the above constituents and 0.0005 g moles of dimethyl tin dichloride (Curve B) against 0.1N sodium hydroxide.

without the metal by the addition of 1 ml of 0.1N NaOH solution. Hence 0.0011 g mole of NaOH is consumed by the complex formed from 0.0005 g mole of dimethyl tin dichloride. This indicates the liberation of two protons. The complex C_1^- can be assumed to be formed by the interaction of dimethyl tin and sodium citrate. Hence the liberation of two protons indicates the formation of C_3^{3-} complex. It has been observed in the experiment (I) and Table I that in the pH range of 6.5 to 8.2, both C_2^{2-} and C_3^{3-} species exist. The same equilibria will hold good in the experiment (IV) (Fig. 4). In this case

$$[\text{Dimethyl tin}] = [C_2^{2-}] + [C_3^{3-}]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Free citrate} &= [H_3\text{Cit}] + [H_2\text{Cit}^-] + [HCit^{2-}] \\ &= X[HCit^{2-}] \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{where } X = 1 + \frac{[H^+]^2}{k_1 k_2} + \frac{[H^+]}{k_2} + \frac{k_3}{[H^+]}$$

$$[\text{Cit}] = [\text{Dimethyl tin}] + X[HCit^{2-}] \quad \dots (6)$$

It can be shown that acid liberated

$$= [C_2^{2-}] + 2[C_3^{3-}]$$

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF K_s VALUES FROM EXPERIMENT-II

pH	[Cit] × 10 ³	[NaOH] × 10 ³	[M] × 10 ³	X	[HCit ²⁻] × 10 ⁶	Y	[C ₂ ²⁻] × 10 ⁴	[C ₃ ³⁻] × 10 ⁴	$K_s \times 10^8$
7.1	23.58	5.315	4.718	41.792	451.4	1.00394	10.49	36.69	2.274
7.2	23.47	5.729	4.695	52.3515	358.6	1.00313	13.93	33.02	2.663
7.3	23.36	6.142	4.673	65.6512	284.5	1.0024	17.54	29.19	3.011
7.4	23.32	6.349	4.665	82.3709	226.4	1.0019	19.1	27.55	2.76
7.5	23.25	6.549	4.65	103.3007	180.1	1.0015	20.8	25.7	2.56
7.6	23.2	6.754	4.641	130.0006	142.8	1.0012	22.55	23.86	2.374
7.7	23.15	6.955	4.63	163.4004	113.3	1.0009	24.38	21.92	2.219
7.8	23.11	7.16	4.622	205.4003	89.97	1.0007	25.88	20.34	2.017
8.0	22.94	7.752	4.587	325.0	36.46	1.0004	32.21	13.66	2.358
8.4	22.78	8.343	4.557	814.7	22.37	1.0 01	38.08	7.49	2.024
9.0	22.62	8.923	4.526	3241.0	5.582	1.00004	44.02	1.24	3.55
9.2	22.62	8.923	4.526	5136.0	3.552	1.00003	44.0	1.26	2.204

Acid neutralised = $[\text{NaOH}] + [\text{HCit}^-] + 2[\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-]$

$$\text{Hence } [\text{C}_3^{2-}] + 2[\text{C}_3^{3-}] = \frac{[\text{NaOH}] + [\text{H}^+] + Y[\text{HCit}^-]}{\dots} \quad (7)$$

where $Y = 1 + \frac{2[\text{H}^+]}{k_2}$

$$\text{or } [\text{C}_3^{3-}] = \frac{[\text{NaOH}] + [\text{H}^+] + Y[\text{HCit}^-]}{[\text{Dimethyl tin}]} \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

$[\text{H Cit}^-]$ has been calculated by equation (6).

The values of $[\text{C}_3^{3-}]$ are obtained by equation (8) and $[\text{C}_3^{2-}]$ has been calculated by subtracting $[\text{C}_3^{3-}]$ from $[\text{Dimethyl tin}]$.

The K_3 values calculated by equation (5-i) from this experiment are recorded in the Table 2. The mean values of K_3 is 2.5×10^{-8} which is exactly similar to that obtained in the experiment (I).

References

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